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Relevance of the Epic Laws of Folk Narrative in the Manipuri Folktales “Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet” and “Sanarembi and Chaishra”

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Abstract:

Manipuri folktales, also called *phunga wari* (stories told around the hearth) or *chak-ngai wari* (stories told while waiting for the meal at night), constitute an important part of Manipuri culture. The tales reflect the values and ethics, the beliefs and traditions of the people of Manipur. They are usually narrated by the elder members (mostly grandparents) of the household to the younger ones in order to convey moral wisdom and truth embedded within the tales, while at the same time giving the listeners a joyful experience. Axel Olrik’s essay “Epic Laws of Folk Narrative”, presented at the Historians’ Congress in Berlin in August 1908, is considered one of the fundamental studies of folklore. Olrik delineates some of the principal laws governing the composition of folk narrative. The epic laws, though well received by European folklorists, must be examined in folklores other than those of Europe. Thus, the paper aims to study the relevance of the epic laws in the well-known Manipuri folktales, namely, “Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet” and “Sanarembi and Chaishra”.

Keywords: Manipur, folklore, folktales, *phunga wari*, epic laws.

Introduction

Alan Dundes’s book *The Study of Folklore* emphasises the importance of formalistic study of folklore. He writes that the analysis of structure and pattern is the rational and valid beginning for the examination and interpretation of folklore. It is because after one has charted the structure, design and formal complexities of folklore, one can effectively describe the types and classification of folklore, to conjecture about their genesis, and to explore their purpose (Dundes 127). Indeed, the form or structure of folktales is crucial as it provides a framework for organising the elements of a story and also for guiding the reader through the narrative. Axel Olrik’s landmark essay “Epic Laws of Folk Narrative” is one such work which studies the form of folktales, particularly the laws governing them. Olrik’s epic laws are better understood when one comprehends his notion of *Sagenwelt* (the realm of *Sage*). Olrik defines *Sage* as “a more comprehensive category” (“Epic Laws of Folk Narrative” 131) incorporating such forms as myths, legends, chronicles, romances, epics, songs and ditties (131). According to him, the laws governing the composition of a particular genre, say a folktale, are not confined to that genre but are equally applicable to other genres such as myth, legend and folksong. Olrik says that the epic laws are the universal rules essential for the formation of all *Sage* genres (131). He considers these laws to be the general principles of *Sage* construction because they limit the freedom of composition of oral literature in a much distinct and rigid way than in literature which is authored and recorded in written form (131).

The realm of *Sage* is a self-contained territory having its truth, rules and order. Alan Dundes remarks that the sphere of *Sage* is a self-sustaining world. With a different reality, system and order of its own, it exists in isolation with no connection with the actual world. The *Sagenwelt* principles greatly outweigh the ordinary laws of “objective reality” (Dundes 129). To Olrik, folklore must follow its principles, not the assumptions of common ordinary existence of everyday life. In short, folklore obeys its laws only, which Olrik terms the ‘epic laws’ – the

superorganic laws which function at a distinctive plane above and beyond the human and popular laws. Olrik's formulation of these laws is comparable to the superorganic conception of culture. Although culture is generated by man, it operates at a domain higher than that of ordinary human life and existence. In the same way, the epic laws have an independent and autonomous existence with no connection with the rules and conditions of the human world. Hasan El-Shamy says that Olrik's principles of folk narrative have an unmistakable superorganic philosophy. He further says that the *Sagenwelt*, strictly bound by these laws, is entirely free from "psychological and social forces" ("Superorganic Theories" 780). In the book *The Study of Folklore*, a similar view is expressed by Alan Dundes on the superorganic quality of Olrik's theory. He also writes that Olrik's treatise on epic laws is a powerful assertion in favour of a superorganic, formal approach to folklore (130).

The first epic laws delineated by Olrik are the law of opening and the law of closing. These laws say that the *Sage* does not begin with sudden action and does not end abruptly. That is, the narrative starts by moving from calm to excitement and ends by making a transition from chaos and turmoil to tranquillity (Olrik 132). Another law of folk narrative composition is the law of repetition. The main objective of this law is to place emphasis on a particular object or event through repetition of actions, words, and so on. Since the description of a particular character, scene, or object is brief and limited in a folk narrative, the law of repetition enables it to achieve the necessary emphasis and focus. Repetition may be an intensifying or a simple one. In comparison to other literary forms, folk narratives are devoid of heavy details in most cases which often prevent the attainment of required emphasis (133). According to Olrik, repetition is the only effective alternative to achieve such emphasis. He further says that repetition is essential not only to intensify the feeling of suspense, uncertainty or anticipation but also to provide details so that the body of the narrative is enlarged (133). Thus, repetition becomes an indispensable means for the *Sage* to obtain its perfect structure.

Closely associated with the law of recurrence of an action, event, or dialogue is the law of three. Olrik says that this law is usually associated with the number three which in turn is also a principle in itself (133). The law of three states that the highest number of characters, objects, or events which occur in a typical folktale is three (133). It differentiates folk narratives from modern literature and also from real life. Nevertheless, Olrik asserts that the law of four often replaces the law of three as in the Indic stories. Moreover, the law of three is found in diminished form in the folksongs of Denmark. It is lost in Icelandic family sagas and also in the tales belonging to the era of ancient Greece and Rome and the medieval period in Europe. Olrik observes that the rule of three maintains its position and presence in true folk narratives which have normally been under the impact of the number three. He says, “The Law of Three reigns supreme in the purely oral versions” (134).

The law of two to a scene states that the maximum number of characters shown in a scene is two. Olrik says that the association of multiple characters acceptable in written literature, is not approved in folk narrative (135). The law of two to a scene leads to its corresponding law, that is, the law of contrast or opposition. Thus, Olrik says that the realm of *Sage* is always sharply divided into two completely opposing groups. The law of opposition is a significant rule of folktale composition with its binary oppositions such as day and night, young and old, life and death, good and evil and so on (135). The law of contrast is based on the antithetical conflict or relationship between the protagonist and the antagonist. The characteristics and actions of the opponent are required to be contrary to those of the protagonist. Olrik further observes that two characters may appear in the same role, neither subordinate nor dominant to each other. The close affinity between the two characters has the possibility of evading the law of contrast and instead becoming the law of twins. The word “twins” denotes actual twins or merely two persons playing a similar part. If, however,

significant roles are assigned to the twins, they will be put through the law of contrast and, correspondingly, will be set against each other.

Other epic principles or laws governing the composition of the *Sage*, outlined by Axel Olrik in his essay, are:

- Folk narrative is always single-stranded. This law points to the simplicity of the folk narrative. With its single thread, it avoids sophistication in plot construction.
- The *Sage* invariably rises to peaks in the form of one or more major tableaux scenes, which are based more on fantasy than on reality. The tableaux scenes convey not a feeling of the evanescence but instead an exceptional quality of endurance through time. They have the power to inhabit themselves in one's mind and imagination.
- The *Sage* has its logic, which is not always measurable by the same standard which assesses the actual world of man and nature. Its fundamental law is the tendency toward animism, miracle and magic.
- Unity of plot is another law of *Sage* composition. The degrees of unity may vary depending on the type of tale. Fairy tales, songs, and local tales have a stronger unity of plot in comparison to myths and heroic sagas.
- The law of concentration on the most important character in a folktale, according to Olrik, is the dominant law of folk tradition (139). That is, a folk narrative focuses on the fate of the principal character or protagonist. Olrik further says that when two heroes or protagonists are present in the narrative, one is at all times the main character. The real charm and appeal lies typically with the female character, though the male persona is the most important character.

Having given an outline of the epic laws of folk narrative, the paper now studies the applicability of the laws in the select Manipuri folktales, namely, “Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet” and “Sanarembi and Chaishra”.

“Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet”

“Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet” is about a tomcat and a Pebet¹. The mother bird lives with her seven little hatchlings in a tree. In the story, the cat pretends to be a monk (hence the name Houdong Lamboiba, where *houdong* means cat and *lamboiba* means monk) with the intention to eat the hatchlings. Pebet, knowing the secret intention of the monk cat, is always on her guard even before her eggs hatch. She has built her nest far out and away from the tree trunk, where no one would reach her. In order to save her babies, she keeps the cat happy until her little ones can fly, by praising him. She knows that if she makes him angry and drives him away, he will eat her babies. When the cat asks Pebet if he is good-looking, she tells him that he is as magnificent as a *shangbai*² filled with rice to its top edge, a pitcher brimmed with water, a string of *ngari*³ arranged in a linear order, and the *tayal*⁴ blooming and thriving among the bamboos (“Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet” 2). Feeling satisfied, the tomcat tells Pebet to feed her babies well and goes away happily. The mother bird gives the same reply as before when the cat revisits her a few days later. She knows that her babies are not fully grown, and that it is not time yet for her to confront the ugly and greedy cat. Meanwhile, she teaches her little ones to fly. She feeds them well, checking their tiny wings closely every day to see if they are strong enough to fly. Day by day, the mother bird watches them grow, and she is happy to see that they are becoming strong and big. She becomes confident enough to challenge the cat and shoo him away. So, when Houdong Lamboiba comes again and asks her the same question: “Hoi, Pebet. How beautiful am I?” (3), she yells back at him, saying that he is hideous with big eyes and a face resembling a pot blackened with soot (3). Seeing Pebet’s unexpected demeanour, the cat becomes angry and pounces on them. Pebet alerts her babies and tells them

to fly. Unfortunately, the cat catches the youngest hatchling, who is somewhat weak and slow to take its flight. Feeling worried but still determined to save her baby, Pebet, using her wit, tells the cat about the best way to eat a pebet. She advises him to give the little hatchling a nice bath and to dry it in the warm morning sun by placing it on a piece of leaf (4). Only then will the cat receive the most satisfying and flavourful taste. Houdong Lamboiba, though greedy and bad, is equally foolish. He follows the advice and instructions given by Pebet. Seeing her little one fully revived and strong after the bath, she cries out, “Fly, echa tombi!” [Fly, my little child] (4). Hearing its mother’s voice, the little bird jumps and flaps its wings, and takes off quickly leaving behind its droppings on the banana leaf. The cat, feeling disappointed, licks the droppings only to find it very tasty and says ruefully that if the droppings are so delicious, the body of the bird would be more toothsome (4). In this way, Pebet protects her children from the greedy cat by outwitting him, who ends up eating only bird droppings.

The study now examines the relevance of the epic laws in “Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet”. The law of beginning and the law of ending are relevant in it. The folktale commences by progressing from a state of serenity to that of disruption and chaos, and then ends by proceeding from the state of disorder to that of tranquillity. The opening paragraph provides a feeling of calmness and cosiness filled with love and hope. This is shown through Pebet and her seven little hatchlings. The feeling of calmness gives way to that of excitement when in the following paragraph the monk cat is introduced and his cunning intentions to eat the young ones of Pebet are revealed. The feeling of excitement gradually increases as the cat starts to visit the bird frequently to check on her babies. It is sustained nearly till the end of the tale as the cat prepares to eat the youngest pebet he has caught. The little pebet taking off quickly in response to the signal given by its mother establishes a state of calmness and relief.

The law of repetition is also present in the folktale. The cat visits Pebet and her babies frequently or repeatedly. The bird, becoming apprehensive of the cat’s repeated visits, teaches

her children to fly day after day till they become strong and healthy. During each visit, the cat asks her the same question, “How beautiful am I?” to which the mother bird gives the same response that he is very handsome. It is on his third visit that the bird chides him severely, pointing to his ugly appearance and ridiculous behaviour. This brings the tale close to the law of three – the cat has visited the pebets three times with an interval of some days in between the visits. He asks the same question three times. Out of the three responses received, two are positive and one is negative.

The law of two to a scene is also relevant in “Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet”. It is only the monk cat and Pebet who interact with each other, though the hatchlings are present in the background. There is no other third character who takes part in the interaction process. Even if three or more characters are present in a scene, it is only two of them who interact, while the remaining characters remain in the background. Since the focus in a scene is on two characters, we can discern the nature, characteristics and personality of the characters. It is at this juncture that the law of contrast becomes evident. Pebet’s motherly love and care for her babies are in direct contrast to the selfishness of the cat. Moreover, she is intelligent, whereas the cat is foolish. It is her wisdom and protectiveness which ultimately save her young ones, whereas for the cat, it is his foolishness that leads him to regret and eat only bird droppings. In short, the characteristics and actions of Pebet (protagonist) provide a stark contrast to those of Houdong Lamboiba (antagonist).

Other epic laws relevant in the folktale are the laws of a single strand of the narrative, coherence of plot, focus on the principal character, and the tableaux scenes. The plot is confined to the bird trying to protect her babies from the cat, who intends to eat them. The whole narrative centres on this single thread. Thus, the unity of plot is strong, which is a characteristic feature of folktales. The law of concentration on a leading character is also relevant in the folktale. Pebet is the protagonist as the narrative focuses on her efforts to nurture and protect

her young ones from the monk cat. Though the title of the folktale refers to both the cat and the bird, the actual interest lies with the bird, who finally outwits the cat. Nevertheless, the cat, also an important character, is a source of humour in the tale. What is comical about the cat is his putting vermilion on his forehead, acting like a monk and chanting the funny nonsensical words “Samu Kaka Lili Ka-Kak” (1). He is amusing in a ludicrous way, particularly towards the end when he, easily fooled by Pebet, follows all her instructions on how to eat a pebet bird in a tasty way. What is even more amusingly absurd is when the cat, with great disappointment, licks the little pebet’s droppings and ponders over the taste of eating the bird. The tableaux scene in the tale occurs when Pebet chides the cat and tells her children to fly. The pebets take off and the angry cat pounces on them. This moment constitutes the striking scene of the folktale.

“Sanarembi and Chaishra”

The folktale “Sanarembi and Chaishra” is about two step-sisters named Sanarembi and Chaishra. After the death of their father, who was a nobleman at the king’s court, their two widowed mothers earn their livelihood by selling firewood gathered from the jungle. Sanarembi is the daughter of Yangkhureima, the first wife of the nobleman, whereas Chaishra’s mother is Sangkhureima, the second wife. Sangkhureima and her daughter Chaishra are envious of Yangkhureima and Sanarembi. They devise ways to harm Sanarembi and her mother. Their plan comes to fruition when Sangkhureima kills Yangkhureima by dropping snakes over her when the two mothers go to the Ngaral lake for fishing. After the death of Yangkhureima, Sangkhureima and her ugly daughter begin to ill-treat Sanarembi and her little brother. Sanarembi is not only a charming young lady but also generous and polite. Her virtue and beauty ultimately capture the attention of the prince of the land when one day Sanarembi and Chaishra go to fetch water. The rest of the folktale continues with Sangkhureima and Chaishra trying to harm Sanarembi, who is now married to the prince, and to destroy her happy

life in the palace. Through their evil plans, they manage to kill Sanarembi. Sanarembi rises from the death to claim her right and happiness. The folktale ends with the defeat and punishment of Sangkhureima and Chaishra for their evil deeds.

“Sanarembi and Chaishra” begins with the narrator introducing the characters in the tale. The first two paragraphs of the folktale give a background of what has happened before leading to the current situation that the characters are in – the death of the nobleman, the family’s poverty following his death, the two wives raising their children, the second wife and her daughter’s jealousy. The opening paragraph provides a seemingly calm atmosphere. However, there is a feeling of an impending catastrophe when we learn that Chaishra and her mother have not for a moment stopped planning to hurt or kill Sanarembi and her mother. The opening of the tale prepares the reader to witness the performance of their evil intentions and plans. In short, the law of opening of folk narrative is evident in “Sanarembi and Chaishra”, which begins by moving from a state of harmony to that of conflict. The law of closing (a movement from excitement to calm) is also clearly noticeable as the tale comes to an end when the prince brings back Sanarembi to the palace and punishes Chaishra by putting her to death for her evil actions. The last line which concludes the tale, “Never forget, truth always triumphs” (“Sanarembi and Chaishra” 25) establishes the tranquillity required in a folktale.

Coming to the law of repetition, there are many instances of actions or situations repeated in the tale in order to build the necessary tension and suspense. The first instance occurs when Sanarembi goes to the Ngaral lake following the instructions given by her mother in her dream. In the dream, the mother, now dead and taking the form of a tortoise, tells Sanarembi to capture the tortoise and place it in the *isaiphu* (an earthen pitcher) for five consecutive days so that she could become alive again. Upon catching a *ngakha* (a small fish) in the first place, Sanarembi lets the fish go. She says, “Oh *ngakha ninganbi*. I am fishing for my mother” (19). She says the exact words and releases the *ngamu* (a different type of small

fish), which she has caught for the second time. Unable to catch the tortoise for quite some time, Sanarembi weeps in despair and apprehension. Nevertheless, with a strong determination, she keeps on fishing and finally catches the tortoise in which the soul of her dead mother dwells. The second instance of repetition occurs when Sangkhureima tells Sanarembi to boil the tortoise for Chaishra, who happens to see it hidden in the pot. Feeling helpless and crying her heart out, Sanarembi places the *isaiphu* containing the tortoise on the fire. As the water begins to boil, the tortoise cries out repeatedly from inside the pot: “Sanarembi, it has reached my ankle” (19), “Sanarembi, it has reached my waist” (19), “Sanarembi, it has reached my chest” (20). When Sanarembi hears the tortoise crying in agony, she immediately pulls out the firewood to put out the fire. She is forced to put back the burning wood under the pot again by her step-mother, who tortures her by pressing a burning piece of wood on Sanarembi’s head. Until well-cooked, the act of Sanarembi pulling out the firewood and Sangkhureima hurting her repeats again and again. Another situation repeated in the narrative is Sanarembi and Chaishra regularly going to the river to fetch water. It is during these visits that the prince of the land sees them and falls in love with Sanarembi. Sanarembi carries a *pun* (an earthen pot) and Chaishra a *sanabun* (a metal pot). The song sung by the prince expressing his love repeats two times: “I dislike the one carrying *sanabun* / I like the one carrying *pun*” (my trans.; 20). Hearing this, Chaishra becomes angry and jealous. The next day, Sangkhureima tells them to exchange their pitchers. Thus, Sanarembi carries the *sanabun*, and Chaishra holds the *pun*. Upon meeting them, the prince sings again: “I dislike the one carrying *pun* / I like the one carrying *sanabun*” (my trans.; 21).

The law of repetition is evident when Sanarembi becomes a lemon growing on a lemon tree in the backyard of the palace. Following the instructions given by Sanarembi in his dream, the prince makes a fence around the lemon tree so that no one can go near it and pluck the lemon. Feeling suspicious of the arrangement, Chaishra tells the royal cowherd to pluck and

eat the fruit. The cowherd plucks it and takes it home. Whenever he is about to eat the lemon, something or the other comes up to prevent him from eating it. He makes three attempts to eat the lemon but fails. In the first attempt, an urgent task arises. He could not find the knife in the second effort. Then, when he found the knife, he could not find the lemon.

The repetition of actions, events, dialogues and songs outlined above is mainly associated with the law of three. Sanarembi catches the tortoise in the third attempt. The tortoise inside the boiling pot cries in agony three times. Responding to the agony, Sanarembi removes the burning firewood three times to save the tortoise. Sangkhureima forces her to put them back again. The act of pulling out and putting back the burning firewood repeats three times. It is only the song of the prince which repeats two times.

The law of two characters in a scene is noticeable in various instances in the folktale: Yangkhureima and Sangkhureima catching fish at the Ngaral lake where the later kills the former by pouring snakes over her; Sangkhureima telling Sanarembi that her mother Yangkhureima is very greedy and stays behind at the lake to catch a bucketful of fish; the dream scene in which Yangkhureima tells about her fatal incident to Sanarembi instructing her to come to the lake the next day and find her who now takes the form of a tortoise; the scene in which Sanarembi pulls out the burning firewood to save the tortoise boiling inside the pot and Sangkhureima forcing her to put them back; the prince singing songs expressing his love to Sanarembi; the dream scene in which Sanarembi (now taking the form of a dove) tells the prince to keep the dove for five days so that she could become a human being again. Thus, numerous scenes conform to the law of two to a scene. Apart from the scenes of two characters interacting, there are other scenes which consist of three characters. Nevertheless, on the whole, the law of two to a scene remains dominant in the folktale.

The law of contrast, a primary rule of epic composition, finds expression in “Sanarembi and Chaishra”. Sanarembi and her mother, Yangkhureima stand in sharp contrast to Chaishra and her mother, Sangkhureima. The title and the opening paragraph of the folktale reflect the contrast. Sanarembi is not only a charming young lady but also generous and polite. She wins the admiration of people who know her. On the other hand, Chaishra is unattractive and has bushy eyebrows. On top of this, she is wicked, selfish, and insolent. Chaishra and Sangkhureima are always envious of Sanarembi and Yangkhureima (17).

The world depicted in “Sanarembi and Chaishra” has its logic, which is not commensurable with that of the real world. In this world, a person, after death, particularly when he or she is put to death, takes a non-human living form such as an animal, a bird, a fruit, a flower or a plant. The person comes to life again when the non-human form is kept secure and safe for five days. The spirit or the soul of the dead person reveals the circumstances of his or her death through dreams, songs or other indications. In the tale, Sanarembi’s deceased mother appears in her dream and tells her to come to the lake to find her who now takes the form of a tortoise. She further tells Sanarembi to catch the tortoise and keep it safe in the *isaiphu* for five successive days (18). Sanarembi’s mother could never regain human form, as the tortoise is cooked and consumed by Chaishra and her mother.

Another instance takes place when Sanarembi, killed by Sangkhureima and Chaishra, turns into a dove. The dove, singing from above a tree, tells the royal cowherd to inform the prince about her. When told by the cowherd, the prince also remembers that he had a glimpse of a dove in a dream not long ago. In the dream, he has been informed that if he keeps the dove for five days, it will become a human. Feeling suspicious, the evil Chaishra, who is now impersonating herself as Sanarembi, kills the dove and makes a curry of it. Chaishra’s action infuriates the prince who throws the dish away at his backyard. After some days, a lemon tree bearing a lemon grows up from where the dish has fallen. Sanarembi, once again, comes to the

prince’s dream and tells him to pick the lemon and keep it for five days inside the *chengphu* (rice pot). The lemon, unknowingly plucked by a royal cowherd and coincidentally kept in the *chengphu*, turns into Sanarembi on the fifth day.

“Sanarembi and Chaishra” abounds in many tableaux scenes. Some of these striking scenes are listed below:

- On the pretext of plucking fruits from the fig tree, Sangkhureima climbs up the tree and then pours the snakes from her basket over Yangkhureima
- Sanarembi cries helplessly while cooking the tortoise for Chaishra
- Sanarembi and Chaishra, while going to the river to fetch water, meet the prince, who sings songs to express his love for Sanarembi
- Sangkhureima pours boiling water on Sanarembi while she is crawling under the bed to pick up her clothes and jewels which Chaishra has thrown away.
- Sanarembi in the form of a dove, singing a song to the royal cowherd so that he can tell the prince about her

The unity of plot in “Sanarembi and Chaishra” is strong. The narrative revolves around the conflict between Sanarembi on the one hand and Sangkhureima and Chaishra on the other. The law of focus on the main character is evident in the folktale. Sanarembi is the main protagonist, an embodiment of goodness in the face of evil. It is significant to note that the evil intentions and actions of Chaishra and Sangkhureima, the principal opponents, drive the narrative, pushing the plot forward. The events that unfold following their evil plans and actions keep the reader engaged with the narrative.

Conclusion

An analysis of the Manipuri folktales “Houdong Lamboiba and Pebet” and “Sanarembi and Chaishra” based on Axel Olrik’s epic laws of folk narrative reveals that many of the epic

laws are applicable in the select folktales. Mention may be made of the laws which find proper expression in these tales, namely the law of beginning and that of concluding, the law of reiteration, the law of an event, action or a dialogue occurring three times, the law of two characters interacting in a scene, the law of opposition or contradiction, the law of narrative cohesion and the law of focus on the main character. Axel Olrik's epic laws helps in understanding the structure and form of the select Manipuri folktales. The applicability of the laws may further be tested in other Manipuri folktales in order to establish a consistency of their relevance in the folktales of Manipur as a whole.

Notes:

1. Pebet is a bird in Meitei mythology and folklore. It is a tiny bird known for its keen intelligence and wit.
2. *Shangbai* is a traditional measuring basket used by the people of Manipur. Weaved from bamboo, it is used to measure the quantity of rice or grains in the process of buying and selling grains.
3. *Ngari* is one of the most popular indigenous food items of Manipur. It is prepared by fermenting a particular fish type known as pool barbs. The fermented fish is used as a condiment in Manipuri dishes.
4. *Tayal* is a creeper, which bears red colour flowers. It grows among bamboo plants. A red *tayal* flower signifies uniqueness.

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